

Daniel Pink's Motivation

Discussion of Daniel Pink's Motivation Idea

Daniel Pink is a successful author of books on motivation, career and business. His books have been translated into 34 languages of the world, in addition, Daniel is a great orator and his speech at the TED Global in Oxford in 2009 is still one of the best video among the many inspiring, enlightening and budorashivshih consciousness speeches delivered at the events held under the auspices of TED. This theory assumes that the main drive which powers human behavior is the drive to respond to rewards and punishments in our environment. As Pink notes, this suggests "human beings aren't much different from horses that the way to get us moving in the right direction is by dangling a crunchier carrot or wielding a sharper stick." Many managers believe that the best way to motivate employees to high results is a monetary reward, bonuses for the result or other "carrots". It turns out, is not so simple. Daniel Pink argues convincingly that the motivation system, based only on the remuneration for results, was not just useless, but in some cases directly harms both employees and the company. There is a need to focus on the natural desire of every human excellence, skill and independence and to hire only those people who have strong internal motivation.

As people have formed a more complex society, we have gradually replaced the system had a new version is more compatible with our working methods and way of life. The core of this new and improved operating system has been revised and updated representation: the people is more than the sum of biological needs. This first motivational force was important still, this is no doubt, but she did not give a complete answer to the question of who we are. We had a second

base incentive to seek pleasure and avoid penalties in the broad sense. It is from this insight, a new operating system, calling it motivation 2.0.

This new way to organize their activities does not exclude the possibility of external rewards. People contributing to the movement of open source projects, did not give a vow of poverty. Participation in these projects can help many of them to strengthen their reputations and hone skills, which in turn will allow them to earn more. Scientists have identified a whole range of motives of these people, but found that “based on having fun intrinsic motivation, that is associated with the creative experiences that accompany the work on this project, is the strongest and most common motivating force.” The researchers found that the vast majority of programmers, they say, are often achieved optimal for solving a condition known as flow. The system Motivation 2.0 impulses of this kind are simply no room (Pink, p.6).

There are two types of formal organizations: commercial and noncommercial. But in the last few years, different people in different countries began to change the rules and recipes to create new organizational structures. They work similarly to commercial organizations, bringing at least a modest income, but their primary goal - to bring substantial public benefits. The purpose of the traditional forms of business profit maximization - ideally consistent with the motivation system 2.0. While the new organization aimed at providing maximum benefit - that does not fit into this outdated operating system because it violates the basic principles. Promotion of autonomy does not constitute a waiver of liability.

Motivation 2.0 implies that if people are given the freedom, they will take time off from work, and that independence is just a way of evading responsibility. Motivation 3.0 takes as its basis the other assumption. It is based on the premise that people want to be responsible for the results of their work and that giving them the opportunity to dispose of the task, their time, their

equipment and their team is the way to achieve this goal. The most well-known company, where the practice has taken root, Google, has long been encouraging developers to devote one day a week working on side projects. In a typical year, more than half of the new Google Suggest born during this period, net of independence.

According to Daniel Pink, The secret to high performance and availability is not our biological needs and not rewards and punishments, and in our deep desire to manage their lives, to develop and expand their abilities and lead a life in which is the goal (purpose) and meaning. Daniel Pink offers a new system of incentives for innovative, creative people; three core elements lie at its core: the freedom to choose, skill, presence of a worthy goal. And these components occur in employees not through the efforts of the leaders, and go inside, because they are natural for thoughtful, intellectually and spiritually developed people. The point of this are to recognize and create conditions and atmosphere for their implementation. A healthy society and a healthy profit organization start with setting goals mission and consider profit as a means towards that goal or as a useful by-product of its achievements.

For example, the author mentions the experiment “candle problem” (candle puzzle). A person who is granted one candle, some matches, a box of pins, all placed on the table is one wall, and are required to attach the candle to the wall so that the wax does not fall down the table. Experimental results show that DL 2.0 (reward for anyone done fast) speed does not make the problem more quickly, because people ignore the use of a box of pins as a tool, which focuses on pins and salt. Also the problem that, if unpinned out of the box and put the experiment participants as two separate things, then they find a solution much faster. The phenomenon unpinned in box makes it just as the box like container pins (the functional

currency, pre-existing function) without thinking of using it for other purposes, is called “functional fixedness”.

Autonomy can be defined as students mostly aspire for independence. In business, it is also the desire to be strong enough, even though students always try to keep up with the idea, independence it's good, and cooperation which is even better. Mastery is most of the students are interested in different (but not all) areas of business, and they periodically try in these directions. In the book “Drive” author have a wonderful phrase that skill is a way of thinking. In summary, we can find a long quotation, which is also supported by a strong research base. Here I just mention that life is for the most part, the big game. And it is important to have the right mindset; students have to make constant efforts to improve their skills in this game. Purpose, maximum profit cannot be the main purpose of the business. For students, yet important issues such as change and improvement.

Work Cited

Pink, Daniel H. Drive: The surprising truth about what motivates us. Penguin, 2011.

